

Differential rice cultivar reactions to *Xoo* strains.

Group	Strain (no.)	Range of av lesion length and disease reaction ^a					Race designation
		IR8 (<i>Xa-11</i>)	IR20 (<i>Xa-4</i>)	IR1545-339 (<i>xa-5</i>)	CAS209 (<i>Xa-10</i>)	DV85 (<i>xa-5</i> , <i>Xa-7</i>)	
<i>Indian strains</i>							
	86						
Group 1a	5	13.0-28.0 (S)	3.0- 7.0 (R)	13.0-20.0 (S)	33.0-40.0 (S)	7.0- 9.0 (R)	Ia
Group 1b	27	16.0-24.0 (S)	10.0-15.0 (S)	11.0-17.0 (S)	31.0-40.0 (S)	7.0- 8.5 (R)	Ib
Group 2	38	19.0-23.0 (S)	11.0-17.0 (S)	17.0-21.0 (S)	20.0-39.0(S)	31.0-36.0 (S)	II
Group 3	2	10.0-18.0 (S)	3.0- 7.5 (R)	14.0-25.0 (S)	19.0-43.0 (S)	23.0-40.0 (S)	III
Group 4	3	11.0-23.0 (S)	3.0- 3.5 (R)	3.0- 9.0 (R)	23.0-46.0 (S)	6.0- 8.0 (R)	IV
Group 5	11	1.0- 3.5 (R)	1.0- 4.0 (R)	3.0- 5.0 (R)	1.0- 4.0 (R)	1.0- 5.0 (R)	-
<i>Nepalese strains</i>							
	36						
Group 1a	7	10.4-16.0 (S)	2.1- 7.7 (R)	10.3-21.7 (S)	10.5-24.6 (S)	3.0- 7.6 (R)	Ia
Group 1b	0	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(R)	Ib
Group 2	7	10.2-23.0 (S)	10.6-21.0 (S)	10.9-20.4 (S)	11.6-24.1 (S)	13.9-25.9 (S)	II
Group 3	8	10.9-21.3 (S)	1.8-6.3 (R)	13.0-19.6 (S)	14.8-19.3 (S)	14.8-22.1 (S)	III
Group 4	1	10.5 (S)	2.2 (R)	5.1 (R)	10.3 (S)	7.6 (R)	IV
Group 5	11	1.3- 8.4 (R)	1.0- 2.7 (R)	1.4- 6.1 (R)	2.2- 9.6 (R)	1.4- 9.4 (R)	-
NX0200	1	6.8 (R)	2.1 (R)	3.6 (R)	12.4 (S)	10.6 (S)	-
NX0216	1	10.5 (S)	5.5 (R)	7.5 (R)	10.8 (S)	13.6 (S)	-

^aR = resistant (<10-cm lesion length), S = susceptible (>10-cm lesion length).

Integrated pest management—insects

Effects of neem and nochi on rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta*

C. Durairaj, National Pulses Research Centre, Vamban Pudukkottai 622303 and M. S. Venugopal, Agricultural Entomology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, India

We conducted a field experiment using IR20 to study the effects of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) and *Vitex negundo* (nochi)

Effect of botanical pest control products on rice bug populations. Madurai, India, 1991-92.

Treatment	Rice bug (no./5 net sweeps) ^a	Decrease over control (%)
Malathion 0.05%	4.0	86.2
Neemark 0.5%	5.0	82.8
Neem oil 2.0%	9.0	69.0
Nochi leaf extract 2.5%	14.3	50.7
Nochi leaf extract 5.0%	18.0	38.0
Neem seed kernel extract 5.0%	17.7	39.0
Control	29.0	-
CD (P = 0.05)	2.54	

^aMean of three replications.

botanical pest control products on rice bug during the second season (Sep 1991-Feb 1992). The insecticide malathion 50 EC was included for comparison (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 20-m² plots and three replications.

Twenty-four hours after spraying, rice bug populations were assessed as the

Developmental biology and host plant range of rice-feeding tiger moth *Cretonotus gangis* (L.)

J. L. A. Catindig, A. T. Barrion, and J. A. Litsinger, IRRI

We studied the development of *C. gangis* on 20 common plant species from families Poaceae (14), Cyperaceae (5), and Commelinaceae (1). Unfed neonate larvae were placed on 25- to 30-d-old individual host plants in 20-cm-diam clay pots enclosed in 10- × 72-cm cylindrical mylar cages with top and side vents of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Ten larvae were released per cage. Each cage served as a treatment, replicated 10 times, in a randomized complete block design in a

number of bugs/five sweeps of a net. Only four rice bugs were recorded in the malathion-sprayed plot, which had a population reduction of 86.2% compared with the control. The next best treatment was Neemark, with 5 bugs. Neem oil, neem seed kernel extract, and nochi were much less effective than malathion and Neemark. ■

non-airconditioned headhouse. Temperature averaged 26.9 ± 1.06 °C. Relative humidity averaged 73.2 ± 4.0%. Host suitability was determined as percentage of larval survival, larval developmental period, larval growth index, and eggs laid by emerging females.

Fecundity was determined on an individual basis for newly emerged moths, which were held in a 65- × 65- × 110-cm rectangular wooden cage frame with sides of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Honey solution (10%) was provided for food. A male was introduced for each caged female.

C. gangis survived to pupation on all 20 plant species, confirming the polyphagous nature of this insect.